

Tronic digital polarimeter model no. EQ 801 at 30 °C in CHCl_3 . IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu FTIR spectrophotometer, ^1H NMR were obtained on a Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz FT NMR) NMR spectrometer in CDCl_3 solution with TMS as an internal reference. The MS spectra were recorded on a Jeol SX-102 FAB mass spectrometer. Purity of the compound was checked by thin layer chromatography using Merck silica gel coated aluminium plates and petroleum ether : ethyl acetate as eluent and iodine vapours as a visualizing agent.

Results and discussion

Thus the synthesized novel *N*-glycosyl benzimidazolyl thiocarbamides exhibits antibacterial and antifungal activities against the organism tested. The method adopted in the synthesis and investigation is simple, efficient and inexpensive in synthesizing pharmacologically important molecule.

Synthesis of peracetyl and perbenzoyl glycosyl isothiocyanate :

The required glycosyl isothiocyanate¹⁸ is prepared by earlier known method by the interaction of glycosyl bromide and lead thiocyanate, while 2-amino benzimidazole was received from Sigma-Aldrich company, all the chemicals were highly purified.

1-Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3-benzimidazolyl thiocarbamide (3a) :

1-Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3-benzimidazolyl thiocarbamide (**3a**) was synthesized by interaction of tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate (0.001 *M*, 0.389 g in 10 ml acetone) (**1a**) and 2-amino benzimidazole (0.001 *M*, 0.133 g in 10 ml acetone) (**2**) in acetone, was refluxed for 6 h while monitoring the reaction by TLC. Acetone was distilled off and resultant syrupy mass was triturated several times with petroleum ether (60–80 °C), to afford white granular solid (**3a**) crystallized

from chloroform petroleum ether (Scheme 2). The characterization of product (**3a**) was established by usual chemical transformation, IR¹⁹, ^1H NMR^{20–24} and Mass²⁵ spectral studies.

1-Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3-benzimidazolyl thiocarbamide (3a) :

Molecular formula $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_9\text{N}_4\text{S}$; yield : 0.491 g; IR (KBr) ν cm^{-1} : 3317 (N-H str.), 2960 (Ali-H str.), 1757 (C=O str.), 1691 (C=N str.), 1641 (N-H bend.), 1512, 1440 (Ar. C=C str.), 1369 (C=S str.), 1240 (C-O str.); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ ppm : 2.018–2.160 (12H, m, acetyl-H), 4.927–5.593 (7H, m, glycosyl-H), 1.25 (1H, s, N-H), 2.182 (1H, s, N-H), 2.367 (1H, s, N-H), 7.219–7.351 (4H, m, Ar-H). Mass analysis : Molecular ion peak (M^+) 523, related observed peaks 422, 413, 371, 177, 176, 135, 134; For [$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_9\text{N}_4\text{S}$] : C, 50.57; H, 4.98; O, 27.58; N, 10.72; S, 6.13; Found : C, 50.50; H, 4.81; O, 27.60; N, 10.58; S, 6.20.

When the above reaction was extended to reaction of acetylated and benzoylated glycosyl isothiocyanates with 2-amino benzimidazole corresponding 1-glycosyl-3-benzimidazolyl thiocarbamides (**3b-f**) have been isolated.

1-Hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-benzimidazolyl thiocarbamide (3b) :

Molecular formula $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{42}\text{O}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{S}$; yield : 0.686 g; IR (KBr) ν cm^{-1} : 3344 (N-H str.), 2980 (Ali-H str.), 1757 (C=O str.), 1649 (N-H bend.), 1512, 1460 (Ar. C=C str.), 1369 (C=S str.), 1246 (C-O str.); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ ppm : 1.942–2.178 (21H, m, acetyl-H), 4.088–5.579 (14H, m, lactocyl-H), 1.259 (1H, s, N-H), 1.942 (1H, s, N-H), 2.360 (1H, s, N-H), 7.193–7.355 (4H, m, Ar-H). Mass analysis : Molecular ion peak (M^+) 811, related observed peaks 771, 770, 701, 660, 331, 176, 134; For [$\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{42}\text{O}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{S}$] : C, 50.37; H, 5.18; O, 33.58; N, 6.91; S, 3.95; Found : C, 50.46; H, 5.20; O, 33.52; N, 6.87; S, 3.98.

Scheme 2

1-Hepta-O-acetyl-β-D-maltosyl-3-benzimidazolyl thiocarbamide (3c) :

Molecular formula C₃₄H₄₂O₁₇N₄S; yield : 0.749 g; IR (KBr) ν cm⁻¹ : 3313 (N-H str.), 2962 (Ali-H str.), 1751 (C=O str.), 1689 (C=N str.), 1637 (N-H bend.), 1508, 1460 (Ar. C=C str.), 1377 (C=S str.), 1244 (C-O str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ ppm : 1.883–2.178 (21H, m, acetyl-H), 3.938–5.517 (14H, m, maltosyl-H), 1.259 (1H, s, N-H), 2.223 (1H, s, N-H), 2.360 (1H, s, N-H), 7.219–7.262 (4H, m, Ar-H). Mass analysis : Molecular ion peak (M⁺) 811, related observed peaks 770, 710, 701, 660, 176, 134; For [C₃₄H₄₂O₁₇N₄S] : C, 50.37; H, 5.18; O, 33.58; N, 6.91; S, 3.95; Found : C, 50.30; H, 5.22; O, 33.62; N, 6.88; S, 3.98.

1-Tetra-O-benzoyl-β-D-glucopyranosyl-3-benzimidazolyl thiocarbamide (3d) :

Molecular formula C₄₂H₃₄O₉N₄S; yield : 0.689 g; IR (KBr) ν cm⁻¹ : 3307 (N-H str.), 3061 (Ar-H str.), 2953 (Ali-H str.), 1741 (C=O str.), 1639 (C=N str.), 1624 (N-H bend.), 1510, 1450 (Ar. C=C str.), 1377 (C=S str.), 1286 (C-O str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ ppm : 4.435–6.353 (7H, m, glycosyl-H), 1.260 (1H, s, N-H), 1.945 (1H, s, N-H), 2.227 (1H, s, N-H), 7.205–8.047 (24H, m, Ar-H). Mass analysis : Molecular ion peak (M⁺) 771, related observed peaks 135, 134; For [C₄₂H₃₄O₉N₄S] : C, 65.45; H, 4.41; O, 18.70; N, 7.27; S, 4.15; Found : C, 65.5; H, 4.40; O, 18.74; N, 7.20; S, 4.18.

1-Hepta-O-benzoyl-β-D-lactosyl-3-benzimidazolyl thiocarbamide (3e) :

Molecular formula C₆₉H₅₆O₁₇N₄S; yield : 1.058 g; IR (KBr) ν cm⁻¹ : 3300 (N-H str.), 3062 (Ar-H str.), 2976 (Ali-H str.), 1735 (C=O str.), 1641 (C=N str.), 1600 (N-H bend.), 1510, 1490 (Ar. C=C str.), 1379 (C=S str.), 1286 (C-O str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ ppm :

4.174–5.872 (14H, m, lactosyl-H), 1.257 (1H, s, N-H), 2.177 (1H, s, N-H), 3.642 (1H, s, N-H), 7.092–8.080 (39H, m, Ar-H). Mass analysis : Molecular ion peak (M⁺) 1245, related observed peaks 1218, 1204, 1186, 135, 134; For [C₆₉H₅₆O₁₇N₄S] : C, 66.55; H, 4.50; O, 21.86; N, 4.50; S, 2.57; Found : C, 66.58; H, 4.54; O, 21.90; N, 4.47; S, 2.59.

1-Hepta-O-benzoyl-β-D-maltosyl-3-benzimidazolyl thiocarbamide (3f) :

Molecular formula C₆₉H₅₆O₁₇N₄S; yield : 1.094 g; IR (KBr) ν cm⁻¹ : 3350 (N-H str.), 3061 (Ar-H str.), 2960 (Ali-H str.), 1735 (C=O str.), 1641 (C=N str.), 1600 (N-H bend.), 1510, 1477 (Ar. C=C str.), 1450 (C=S str.), 1273 (C-O str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ ppm : 4.412–6.273 (14H, m, lactosyl-H), 1.257 (1H, s, N-H), 1.888 (1H, s, N-H), 3.588 (1H, s, N-H), 7.205–8.113 (39H, m, Ar-H). Mass analysis : Molecular ion peak (M⁺) 1246, related observed peaks 1204, 1186, 1142, 486, 135, 134; For [C₆₉H₅₆O₁₇N₄S] : C, 66.55; H, 4.50; O, 21.86; N, 4.50; S, 2.57; Found : C, 66.52; H, 4.54; O, 21.90; N, 4.48; S, 2.60.

Antimicrobial activity :

These newly synthesized thiocarbamides were screened for their microbial activity against different pathogenic microbes for their antibacterial and antifungal activities using well method²⁶.

Procedure for antimicrobial screening :

Media used (Nutrient broth) : Peptone – 10 g, NaCl – 10 g and yeast extract 5 g, Agar 20 g in 1000 ml of distilled water. Initially, the stock culture of bacteria were revived by inoculating in broth media and grown at 37 °C for 18 h. The agar plates of the above media were prepared and wells were made in the plate. Each plate was inoculated with 18 h old culture (100 μ L, 10⁴ cfu) and

Table 1. Physiochemical and analytical data of compounds (3a-f)

Sr. No.	Product	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Found (Required) (%)		R _f Pet. ether : EtOAc (3 : 7)	[α] _D ³⁰ (c in CHCl ₃)
				N	S		
1.	3a	94	151	10.56 (10.72)	6.10 (6.13)	0.35	-140 (c, 0.05)
2.	3b	85	120	6.87 (6.91)	3.89 (3.95)	0.5	-180 (c, 0.01)
3.	3c	92	129	6.88 (6.91)	3.86 (3.95)	0.65	-120 (c, 0.01)
4.	3d	89	154	7.20 (7.27)	4.18 (4.15)	0.55	-120 (c, 0.01)
5.	3e	86	140	4.53 (4.50)	2.53 (2.57)	0.45	-95 (c, 0.01)
6.	3f	88	159	4.48 (4.50)	2.60 (2.57)	0.46	-176 (c, 0.01)

spread evenly on the plate. After 20 min the wells were filled with different concentrations of samples. All the plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h and the diameter of inhibition zones were noted in mm (Table 2).

Table 2. Antibacterial and antifungal activities of compounds (3a-f)

Compd.	Inhibition zone diameter (mm)				
	Bacteria			Fungi	
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
3a	13	14	12	21	18
3b	12	17	8	14	16
3c	12	9	24	15	14
3d	9	8	7	19	16
3e	11	10	23	16	17
3f	7	9	25	19	14
Gentamicine	25	25	25	–	–
Nystatin	–	–	–	23	23

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